

**CORRESPONDENCE BETWEEN STRESS FIELDS AND DAMAGE ZONES AHEAD OF
CRACK TIP OF COMPOSITES UNDER MODE I AND MODE II DELAMINATION**

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ABSTRACT

The Stress field ahead of the crack tip of a split laminate specimen loaded under mode I and Mode II delamination has been determined by means of a finite element analysis. The results have then been compared to the observed damage zone developed ahead of the crack tip for the same loading conditions. A direct correspondence has been found between the stress fields, damage zones observed, and resistance to delamination of composites for this modes of delamination fracture.

INTRODUCTION

Fiber-reinforced composite materials usually offer poor resistance to delamination. As a result, a complete understanding of the delamination process is needed to properly design composite structures and develop materials with improved fracture toughness characteristics. An important area of investigation is the determination of the stress field ahead of the crack tip for the various modes of delamination fracture (i.e. mode I, mode II, and mode III), by means of finite element analyses. Furthermore, these stress fields can be related to the corresponding observed damage zones that develop ahead of the growing crack as determined from in-situ observations in the scanning electron microscope. This combination of analyses with direct observation of delamination has been very useful in

developing an overall understanding of the relationship between macroscopic resistance to crack propagation and modes of delamination fracture.

In this investigation, the stress field ahead of the crack tip of a split laminate specimen loaded under mode I and mode II delamination conditions has been determined by means of a finite element analysis. The results were then compared to the observed damage zone developed ahead of the crack tip for the same loading conditions.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The determination of the stress field ahead of the crack tip of the split laminate specimen loaded under mode I and mode II was accomplished by first generating a two dimensional mesh 152.4 mm long and 2.54 mm thick consisting of 791 nodes and 294 elements as shown in Figure 1a. Triangular six-noded elements were used around the crack tip with mid-side nodes displaced to the quarter point [1], and a substantial refinement of the mesh around the crack tip was made to overcome the difficulty imposed by the stress singularity present at the crack tip. This has been a linear analysis made with a finite element algorithm developed by Henriksen [2]. The algorithm is based on a nonlinear code updated with Lagrangian formulation using six and/or eight noded isoparametric elements with two degrees of freedom per node. Elastic constants for a unidirectional laminate of AS4/3502 graphite/epoxy composite to be used in the analysis were obtained from Hercules [3].

Mode I loading was simulated by applying a symmetric load at the cracked end of the mesh as shown in Figure 1b. Mode II loading was introduced by asymmetrically loading the cracked end (see Figure 1c). The load level applied corresponds to approximately the load at onset of crack growth for these two modes of failure, as determined from experimental measurements in combination with beam linear beam theory [4]. Stress contour plots were obtained from the output data and the stress distribution was plotted as a function of distance ahead of the crack tip.

Two sizes of split laminate specimens were used for direct observation of delamination in the scanning electron microscope, one 38.1 mm long, 5.08 mm wide and 1.14 mm thick, and the other 30.48 mm long, 5.08 mm wide, and 1.14 mm thick. Hercules unidirectional AS4/3501-6 graphite/epoxy composite material was used for mode I and mode II observations of the damage zones, respectively. The real time observations

(a) Finite element mesh consisting of 791 nodes and 264 elements.
(Dimensions in millimeters)

(b) Mode I boundary conditions.

(c) Mode II boundary conditions.

Figure 1. Finite element mesh and boundary conditions.

of delamination were made in a JEOL-35 scanning electron microscope. Mode I delamination was achieved by pushing a wedge into the precracked portion of the longer split laminate specimens, using the tensile stage of the scanning electron microscope. The wedge was sufficiently blunt to ensure that it remained well away from the crack tip, giving essentially pure mode I loading. Mode II delamination was achieved by means of a specially designed three point bend fixture installed to the tensile stage of the scanning electron microscope. All surfaces observed were coated with a 150 Å thick gold/palladium film to minimize charging effects associated with the nonconductive nature of the epoxy matrix of the composite. The experimental results were recorded on standard tri-x film.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figures 2 and 3 show the finite element results for both mode I and mode II loading. Figure 2a is a S_{yy} (normal) stress contour plot from the vicinity of the crack tip for mode I loading. The normal stress S_{yy} which for this loading and geometry is the principal normal stress S_2 , rapidly decreases ahead of the crack tip. Figure 2b corresponds to the S_{xy} (shear) stress contour plot for a mode II condition. Note how the shear stress drops off much more slowly with distance ahead of the crack tip than does the normal stress for mode I loading (Figure 2a). Furthermore, the shape of the stress field is more narrow and elongated. For this loading condition, $S_{xy} = \text{maximum shear stress} = S_1$. Figure 3 shows the stress distribution as a function of distance ahead of the crack tip for mode I and mode II. In the case of the normal stress for mode I, the stress drops off rapidly until it is compressive at a distance of 0.76 mm ahead of the crack tip. Finally, it gradually approaches a zero stress level at approximately 8 mm from the crack tip which is maintained all the way to the end of the beam. It should be noted that the compressive stresses observed are not expected to significantly influence the fracture mode at the crack tip because it develops far enough away from the crack tip. In the case of the shear stress distribution ahead of the crack tip for mode II, it monotonically decreases to a constant value. As it can be seen, the shear stress ahead of the crack tip for mode II loading decays much slower than the normal stress for mode I loading. These results indicate that the stress concentration at the crack tip is distributed over a larger distance for mode II loading than for mode I loading. For mode II, the extent

Figure 2. Stress contour plots.

of the stressed material above and below the center plane being much smaller than for mode I, as seen in the stress contour plots in Figure 2.

Figure 4 corresponds to the observed damage zones developed ahead of the crack tip for both mode I and mode II delamination of AS4/3501-6. The mode I damage zone is characterized by extensive microcracking of the resin extending at least 90 microns ahead of the macroscopic crack tip and approximately 7.5 microns above and below the primary plane of crack advance. In the case of mode II, the damage zone extends much further ahead of the crack tip (at least 180 microns) than the mode I damage zone, and is approximately 5 microns in extent above and below the primary crack plane.

Figure 3. Stress distribution ahead of crack tip for mode I and mode II.

A careful comparison of the stress fields of Figures 2,3 and the damage zones shown in Figures 4 for mode I and mode II delamination, reveals a direct correspondence between them. The more gradual decrease in the magnitude of the shear stress with distance from the crack tip for mode II (Figure 3), along with the elongated shape of the shear stress contour plot seen in Figure 2b indicates that the stress concentration at the crack tip is distributed over a larger range, causing the size of the damage zone ahead of the crack tip to be elongated (Figure 4b). In contrast, the rapid decay of the magnitude of the normal stress for mode I with distance from the crack tip (Figure 3) and the more circular shape of the normal stress contour plot of Figure 2a indicate that the stress concentration at the crack tip is much more localized, causing the extent of the damage zone ahead of the crack tip to be smaller than for mode II delamination. Furthermore, the extent of the stressed material above and below the plane of delamination is seen in the stress contour plots to be much smaller for mode II than for mode I. Thus, the damage zone (Figure 4) changes from wide to narrow as one goes from mode I to mode II. These findings indicate that the greater resistance to delamination for mode II loading ($G_{IIC} = 570 \text{ J/m}^2$) than for mode I loading ($G_{IC} = 190 \text{ J/m}^2$) in AS4/3502, a similar material as AS4/3501-6, may be explained in part as resulting from the different decay rate of the stress field and the

(a) Mode I damage zone developed ahead of crack tip.

(b) Mode II damage zone developed ahead of crack tip.

Figure 4. Damage zones ahead of crack tip.

resulting difference in damage zone size and shape ahead of the crack tip for the two loading conditions.

It should be noted that even though the finite element analysis assumed global linear elastic orthotropic material behavior, it still predicted the overall trend in damage zone size and shape, despite the actual nonlinear behavior of composites in the crack tip region.

When dealing with damage zones development, the effect of the state of stress, namely plane stress versus plane strain, may be important. This is particularly true where the principle shear stress plays a role in the deformation or fracture process. The damage zones shown in Figure 4 are

(a)

(b)

Figure 5. Von-Mises stress for mode I and mode II loading.

obviously from the edge of the specimen where a plane stress condition occurs. Therefore, in order to have a first order approximation as to the effect the difference in the state of stress at the surface of the

specimen where our direct observations are made, and at the center where plane strain conditions prevail, the Von-Mises stress for mode I and mode II was plotted as function of distance ahead of the crack tip. The results in Figure 4a indicate that for mode I, the difference in the Von-mises stress (or root mean square shear stress) in plane stress versus plane strain is approximately 10%. In the case of mode II, the difference is negligible as evidenced in Figure 4b. Therefore, it appears that for these orthotropic materials, the difference between plane stress and plane strain is not too significant and our surface observations of damage zone size and detail should not be very different than subsurface behavior. Previous studies in which the post mortem appearance of the fracture surface near a free edge to that at the center of a specimen are consistent with this interpretation [6]. A final observation from Figure 4 is that the stress field ahead of a crack tip decays much more slowly for an orthotropic material with the crack parallel to the fibers than for an isotropic material.

CONCLUSION

In summary, it has been found that the different size and shape of the damage zone observed when comparing mode I to mode II delamination is consistent with the difference in the size and shape of the stress field predicted by the finite element analysis. Furthermore, these differences are also consistent with the difference in resistance to delamination of brittle graphite/epoxy composites for the two types of delamination studied. Also, there appears to be a very small difference between plane stress and plane strain states of stress for orthotropic materials. Therefore, the damage zones observed during in-situ delamination in the scanning electron microscope should not vary significantly from the actual damage zone that develops at the center of the specimens (plane strain damage zone).

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